

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION.

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Abstract This article is about advantages and disadvantages of using innovative technologies in education. Positive and negative aspects of them are clarified with examples. How they effect on students, teachers is explained. For example, accessing to information, finding information easily, new teaching methods, excessive using of technology, educational problems.

Key words: methods, innovative, technology, Whatsapp, email, information, education, smartphone, laptop, computer, lesson, problem, Internet.

Introduction.

The use of innovative technologies in the educational system not only increases the effectiveness of teaching, but also causes a number of problems. The rapid development of technology has had a significant impact on the lives of students. From smartphones to computers, technology has permeated all aspects of student life. Therefore, factors that are dangerous for users also appeared. In the followings advantages and disadvantages of the innovations technologies are clarified.

Main part

Access to information is easier. through email, whatsapp and other means of communication, students can easily access and use their academic assignments. Students have the opportunity to regularly engage in their lessons through this method. Students who used to wait in line in libraries to meet with a teacher or collect information can now do these tasks quickly and easily using smartphones and laptops. The use of technology in education has made it easier for teachers to

perform their tasks, for example, information about the results of an exam or test during the lesson, as well as information about the performance of students is automatically found.

Good preparation for the future, in the era of rapid development of innovative technology, students can be prepared for life after education. An excellent curriculum that includes scientific and technological education will guide students to a bright future. Students will be able to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills required in the competitive labor market. Lessons conducted with the help of various technological tools will be very useful for students' employment in the future. Leadership in interpretation helps to develop skills such as teamwork.

Finding materials easily to study. Thanks to smartphones, tablets or laptops, students can easily find learning materials. If earlier students had to carry heavy books and flip through several books endlessly to find a single piece of information, now thanks to innovative technologies, all this has become easier. Students can now find the information they want quickly and easily.

New teaching methods were developed. Thanks to the development of modern technologies, teachers discover new innovative methods for themselves. With the emergence of various digital teaching systems and educational technologies, positive changes began to occur in the course of the lesson. New teaching methods have been discovered that incorporate the latest technologies and offer students comprehensive learning methods.

With the discovery of technology, along with creating convenient opportunities for users, it also showed its negative aspects. This was initially manifested in its incorrect use.

Excessive use of technology (for example, smartphones, laptops) can seriously harm human health. It causes impairment of brain function and vision. Relying on the possibilities of innovative technology weakens the ability of human thinking. users use ready-made answers instead of thinking. Currently, various dangerous

groups and currents operate on the Internet. Leaving control over the use of the Internet by students and pupils can cause serious problems.

Educational problems. As innovative technologies are applied to education, they create a number of conveniences for teachers as well as create a number of difficulties. In order to use the innovative technologies entering education and apply them in the course of the lesson, teachers should have knowledge about these technologies and know how to use them. cheating in exams. Today, students look for ready-made answers on the Internet, where there is an endless source of information, instead of using what little knowledge they have during exams. As a result, during the assessment, their real knowledge and shortcomings will not be revealed, and a defect in their knowledge and skills will appear.

Conclusion

In conclusion, innovative technologies have both positive and negative sides. Misusing them can cause serious problems for learners. Their negative effects are not only educational but also, related health. It is important to differentiate beneficial and harmful aspects of innovative technologies.

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